

Room Temperature Ferromagnetism in Group I Elements Codoped ZnO:Mn Nanomaterials

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Abstract

ZnO is a wide band gap II–VI semiconductor known for its multifunctional properties and interesting applications in the field of magneto-electrics and magneto-optic devices [1]. ZnO based DMS materials have been attracting much interest of potential spintronics devices such as spin-valve transistors, spin light emitting diodes, and non-volatile storage [2]. Dietl et al. predicted theoretically the room temperature ferromagnetism (RTFM) behavior in Mn doped ZnO [3]. In this present work, we report that the structural, optical and magnetic behaviour of monovalent group I elements (Li⁺ Na⁺ K⁺) codoped ZnO:Mn nanoparticles (NPs). The Mn doped and Group I elements codoped ZnO:Mn nanoparticles were prepared by co-precipitation method. The single crystalline phase formation of prepared NPs was confirmed by XRD and Raman spectroscopic technique. The presence of lattice defects was identified from the Raman and EPR spectral analysis. The room temperature ferromagnetic behaviour of prepared NPs was observed from VSM analysis. The presence of lattice defects induced ferromagnetism in prepared NPs. The observed results are discussed and reported.

Keywords: Nanoparticles, Room Temperature Ferromagnetism, Effect of Lattice Defects

Reference

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